

CARPET YARN PRODUCTION IN KARAKALPAKS

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Annotation: The article was the most important in national carpet weaving and the initial processes in the production of threads that directly affect the quality of the carpet, as well as the basis of the carpet, were written on the basis of a comparative analysis of karakalpak carpet weaving with the carpet weaving of other peoples.

Keys words: Carpet, Bukhara sheep, Kazakh sheep, autumn cut, spring cut, "Ashar", Patlaw", Jackke Parsan, Teshik-Kala.

Carpet making has always been an important process for Karakalpaks. Because in the middle of the 19th century, the demand for carpet products was very high. Almost all household and household items are carpeted. According to Aygul Pirnazarova, head of the ethnographic department of the Karakalpak State Art Museum named after I.V. Savitskiy: "Every girl had to know how to weave carpet patterns. Because these properties, skillfully woven, were criticized by older people. That's why the people have kept the saying: "It's not a smart bride, but a smart bride." Therefore, the skill of women, their readiness to become bridesmaids, was tested through the carpets they made for their home. In order to create aesthetically pleasing, durable carpets, it is necessary that the threads intended for carpet weaving be of high quality. Special processes have been carried out for this purpose. Sheep wool was chosen as a high-quality yarn. However, not all sheep had the same fiber. Sheep are specially selected for it. V.G. Moshkova lists the best sheep wool in Central Asia in the production of yarn. According to him: "The best bright, fresh sheep are Karakul (Bukhara) sheep. Thus, in addition to fat-tailed (Kazakh) sheep, Ordova and Khotan sheep were brought to the Fergana oasis, and the fur of Turkmen sheep was preferred in the Turkmen tribe of the Bukhara Khanate. In some villages around the market, a special type of Turkmen sheep was found - a light-haired white Penda sheep. At the end of the 19th century, it was widely used in the villages of the Penda oasis. Yomud Turkmens preferred Doloq and Shirak sheep breeds in weaving. [2,30-31] And in the land of the Karakalpaks, according to A. Otemisov: "Wool fabrics are mainly made from local sheep: sheep, Kazakh sheep, and secondly, camel wool" [3,68] - informs. Also, sheep were not always given forty after selection. The Karakalpaks chop their sheep twice a year - in spring and autumn. He called

the spring cut down wool, and the autumn cut down wool. "In autumn, the cut was cut as if it had grown 2-3 centimeters before the cold. She killed the sheep in the summer. In summer their wool is quite dry. He calls it summer forty. There were separate reasons for this. The difference between spring and autumn cutting is taken into account: spring wool is long and soft, while autumn wool is strong and hard. "The cut that was preferred for making carpets, that is, for making yarn, was considered a spring cut, and the crown was considered very good for dressing. Because the spring cut is long, it is convenient to make yarn, and the spindle cut is convenient for spinning, and the autumn cut is short, the informant says. If the wool was soft, it would be difficult to combine, and to obtain a good harvest, the yarn had to be well-crafted. However, depending on the types of products, geographical environment, and living conditions, the stages may vary until the product is ready. For example, the threads made from sheep wool were made in Turkmenistan in the following way. "For wool yarn; 1) washing and drying the wool, rubbing it up to half, it will be a soft mass. 2) combing in the comb. 3) coloring" [6,181]. The process of washing sheep among the Karakalpaks differs from other peoples. According to the information provided by the carpet weaver Bayram Gaypov from the city of Khojeli, "among the Karakalpaks, the fat sheep that are killed in the month of May are washed." Because they are long dust and dirty. However, it is not necessary to wash the autumn cut because it is small. After that, special wool is combed with a comb. However, today there are places equipped by special entrepreneurs. Special equipment is ready for the spinning process. And after that we'll twist it with a spindle, and we'll do it it can be spun in a comfortable thickness. At the end we will paint." The informant shared his valuable information [7]. After the yarn was ready, our women-masters began to weave carpet weaves necessary for the household. Of course, bringing wool to the level of yarn was a very difficult task. For such works, assistance was organized among the Kyrgyz people, which is a tradition that goes back to ancient times, and the people called it "Ashiw" (holiday) "There were women artisans in every village. When a family wants to weave a rug or weave a carpet, neighbors come and measure colors and decorative compositions, draw a pattern, and some cut wool. After the completion of rituals, which are a symbol of such unity, that is, after the harvest is ready, the host gave food to the helpers in gratitude and sometimes presented them with greetings. It should be noted that in Karakalpak families, every woman should have mastered the methods of spinning and weaving. However, unfortunately, today this program is not available. Such traditions, which are

highly valued among Turkmens, are still preserved.

Among the Karakalpaks, cotton was widely used as a raw material in the production of yarn. In the early Middle Ages, during the period of the African dynasty, the remains of cotton fabrics were studied by archaeologists. Cotton fields have been discovered in the vicinity of the Great Guldyrys [9,144]. In addition, according to the finds of clothing made of wool, cotton, silk, found in the cultural layers of the cities of Jacke Parsan, Teshik-Kala, and Burkut-City, it proves the development of textile crafts. High-quality fabrics are woven from cotton. According to written sources, "When the Arab commander Qutayba conquered Khorezm, he demanded this high-quality cotton fabric as a tribute" [10, 79-80]. It is clear from this that in the period of the Afrigians, the areas where they now lived were well developed in the production of cotton. But this did not last long. Because it was not easy for the ethnic groups living in the territory of medieval Karakalpakstan. There was a succession of dynasties. In such cases, in the 10th-12th centuries, the Karakalpaks acquired the name "Karakalpak." After this, the first migration of the Karakalpaks took place. At the beginning of the 13th century, the state of Kerder collapsed after the invasion of Genghis Khan, especially when his troops turned the Amudarya to the Uzbai (Caspian Sea). The lower reaches of the river were dry. "The level of the Aral Sea has decreased. Due to the desertification of the lands, the Karakalpaks were forced to migrate to other lands. However, regardless of the countries they lived in, the Golden Horde Khanate (XIV-XV), the Uzbek Khanate (XV), the Nogai Khanate (XV-XVI), the Kazakh Khanate (XVI-XVIII), and the Khiva Khanate (XIX) lived as a separate country with their own system of governance. Of course, no matter how much he lives with his own policy, such situations will not fail to affect the spiritual life of the people, especially their economy. At the same time, there was a significant economic loss in the desertification of the flowering land, and almost no cotton was planted in the territory of Karakalpakstan until it was incorporated into the Khiva Khanate. The composition of the Khiva Khanate was planted in small quantities. "Cotton was very expensive in the khanate, so buying it easily cost the Karakalpaks a lot of money. In the middle of the 19th century, they learned to grow cotton from their neighbors, the old peasant Uzbeks. However, it can be assumed that during this period, the cultivation of cotton was of interest to the Karakalpaks only for consumption. The most regrettable was the disappearance of cotton fields in the early Middle Ages as a result of political changes. However, the interest of neighboring peoples in the climate of Central Asia was strong. In the middle of

the 19th century, Patsha Russia conquered the Khiva Khanate. This meant that the Karakalpaks who were part of the Khiva Khanate had a great influence. The main reason for the colonization was the empire's interest in cotton. In the 1950s and 1960s, the Russian Empire renewed its efforts to penetrate Central Asia. Because during these years, due to the civil war in the United States, Russia's cotton purchases from that country were significantly reduced. Russian industrialists now considered that only Central Asian cotton could be produced from this difficulty" [13, 40]. At the same time, the Tsar of Russia intensified cotton cultivation compared to other crops. Of course, the seeds are buttercotton fiber is yarn. It is natural that among the population, in addition to wool yarn, the production of cotton yarn is developed. V.G.Moshkova writes about the main reason for this: "By the end of the 19th century, animals living a nomadic and semi-nomadic way of life began to move to agriculture due to various political and economic reasons" [2,19]. If we turn to the second opinion: "The collections of the Russian Ethnographic Museum express the same opinion, the main types of textile practices of the Karakalpaks of the Amu Darya Delta developed from the end of the 19th century until the second half of the 20th century" [14]. This development was facilitated by the widespread development of cotton growing in the region. After the annexation of the Russian Empire, the varieties of cotton began to change among the Karakalpaks. Our women began spinning cotton yarn and weaving needles for the household. Of course, as there is a technique for processing wool yarn, there are different methods for obtaining cotton yarn. This was reported by Murineserova Bibi from the Khojeli district: "First, cotton is separated from seeds with the help of a scraper, then it is beaten with the help of a beater until it becomes like silk. At the end, yarn is made using a spindle" [15]. As we mentioned above, many women were working in cotton making the necessary tools for their lives. They mainly made ornamental items in the barn or items that firmly hold the barn. About the fact that almost all Karakalpak carpet products were made of cotton, Professor T.A. Zhdanko writes in his article: "Aqbasqur, janbaw, akkur, egilbaw, kergi eshikchasi (basis) is made of cotton, and the pattern is made of wool" [16,381]. It is clear that by adding wool and cotton, it was possible to make textile products. According to information provided by carpet weaver Jiemurtava Asia: "The increase in demand for cotton in yarn production lies in its strength. Compared to wool, cotton is smooth and easily weaves. Also, the reason why most of the black household items are made of cotton is due to the technique, that is, because the clothes are woven in a pile, the wool sticks and breaks. This will take up a lot of our time. The cotton won't

get caught, and the unattached string won't break. But it is necessary to get used to it. There is an ancient method of "Patlaw" among the people, which contributes to the strength of the thread. Let's pour a bowl of flour into the big pot and boil it. We put our threads on the finished cloth and boil it once." [17] The wool fibers are joined together and strengthened. In particular, wool threads are boiled in this way. As we can see, cotton has been valued in our household from ancient times to the present day. Whether in carpet weaving or in other textile industries, our next raw material is camel wool. However, it is practically extinct, not widespread today. The main reason for this is that our households are hardly equipped. A. Utemisov wrote about this: "Before the revolution, the camel's wool was scarce among the Karakalpaks, because the camel did not keep much household." Furthermore, P.P. Ivanov writes: "Karakalpak women are limited to the processing of camel wool." Therefore, it can be concluded that the Karakalpaks used camel wool only for clothing. And among the Kyrgyz, the camel is highly valued, first of all, for migration. Secondly, it is widely used for wool. Surprisingly, according to K.I. Antipina's writing,... "in the production of cloths, wool from the camel's back was used, and cloths made of young camels were highly valued.....The carpet was made of wool from the camel's neck and knee" [19,19]. There is an opportunity to produce various high-quality products from the wool of each camel member. In this case, it should be accepted as the magic of nature, the attraction given to people. Also, "Turkmens used camel wool as the best option for making yarn. They were harvested once a year in May-June, during the hot weather. Even camel wool is not dyed so that it does not lose its quality. It can be observed that the quality of camel wool is valued to such an extent.

In conclusion, carpet production is one of the material assets of the people, the nation. By looking at what yarn the base of the carpet was made of, we can understand how that people lived or what was important in their lives. Because we saw above that the carpet thread is made of different animal wool. Therefore, when we work on the basis of comparative analysis, which population is shown, that population used the fibers of animals that have been kept a lot in life. Therefore, carpet ornaments express the spirituality of the people, while carpet fabrics describe socio-economic life.

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